

Legal aspects of HET: Brazil

[WP3 – Human enhancement]

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Executive summary

In this report we present an analysis of the Brazilian national legislation on issues related to Human Enhancement Technologies (henceforth simply HET). The SIENNA Project defines “human enhancement as a modification that aims to improve human performance through biotechnology interventions. However, there is no established term for human enhancement in the Brazilian law. Human enhancement is not directly addressed in the national legislation. On the other hand, it is possible to find in the Brazilian legislation some specific laws and regulations that address particular issues related to human enhancement, even though the expression “human enhancement” itself, or one of its counterparts in Portuguese, does not occurs in these documents.

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- **Table 1:** List of acronyms/abbreviations

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ANVISA	Brazilian Health Regulatory Agency (<i>Agencia Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária</i>) http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/
CFM	Federal Medical Council (<i>Conselho Federal de Medicina</i>) https://portal.cfm.org.br/
HE	Human Enhancement
HET	Human Enhancement Technologies
IMD	Implanted Medical Devices
IVF	In Vitro Fertilization
PGD	Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis
Port.	Portuguese language
SUS	Unified Health System (<i>Sistema Único de Saúde</i>) http://portalms.saude.gov.br/sistema-unico-de-saude

Table 1: List of acronyms/abbreviations

1. Introduction

The objective of this report is to analyse some aspects of the Brazilian law that are relevant for a legal analysis of HET. The primary method used here is desk research and consultation with country experts. The desk research followed the guidelines established in the SIENNA Handbook, and particularly the doctrinal and functional methods of legal analysis.

HET enable individuals to perform cognitive or physical functions better than other individuals would normally do. In the current literature on human enhancement, other forms of enhancement such as, for instance, moral enhancement and cosmetic (or aesthetic) enhancement have also been discussed. Throughout this report, though, we focus mostly HET for the purpose of cognitive and physical enhancement.

Human enhancement becomes especially apparent with the use of new medical technologies. These technologies are usually devised in order to enable individuals who suffer from some physical or psychic disorder to recover their cognitive or physical capacities in such a way that they can achieve the same level of cognitive or physical performance of healthy individuals. As it happens, though, the same technologies that can be used to treat an individual can sometimes also be used to enable healthy individuals to perform better than other healthy individuals in the same age range. From a legal point of view, it is not clear how to classify or how to regulate these technologies, for they can work both as a form of “treatment” (or “therapy”) to some individuals, and as a form of “enhancement” to other individuals. While treatment is extensively regulated in virtually any country, enhancement, on the other hand, is not even mentioned in most jurisdictions. In Brazil, for instance, there is no specific legislation that regulates this matter.

Yet, lack of legislation has not prevented individuals to pursue different forms of enhancement, even if they would not themselves describe their practices with the vocabulary of HE. In Brazil, some forms of HE have already become widespread. In this section, we briefly review five areas of HE that have been pursued in Brazil, namely: [1] cognitive enhancement by means of drugs; [2] physical

enhancement in sports; [3] genetic human enhancement by means of IVF and PGD; [4] human enhancement through prosthetic limbs and microchip implants; [5] and aesthetic enhancement through cosmetic surgeries.

[1] Cognitive enhancement by means of drugs

Many students in Brazil are reported to have used drugs such as methylphenidate (*Port.: Ritalina*) and modafinil (*Port.: Stavigile*) as cognitive enhancers.¹ Methylphenidate is usually prescribed to treat Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), and modafinil to treat narcolepsy. But there is some evidence that these drugs also enable healthy individuals to perform better in some cognitive tests.² It is well known that most individuals who have been using methylphenidate as a cognitive enhancer are students.³ There is also some evidence that many women have been using cognitive enhancers in order to couple with competition in the job market while having to take care of their children as well.⁴ Thus far, however, no nationwide systematic study has been conducted to assess the number of students who have been using medical drugs for the sole purpose of cognitive enhancement in Brazil. Drugs such as methylphenidate and modafinil cannot be bought over the counter. Their purchase requires a special prescription, which is more rigidly controlled by the government. This requirement, named “Technical Regulation on Substances and Medicinal Products subject to Special Control”, was introduced by Decree (*Port.: Portaria*) Nº 344, from 12 May 1998 (*Port.: Regulamento Técnico sobre Substâncias e Medicamentos Sujeitos a Controle Especial*).⁵ When drugs such as methylphenidate, modafinil and similar substances are consumed for the purpose of cognitive enhancement, they are also popularly referred to as *smart drugs* or more frequently “pílula da inteligência”.⁶

[2] Physical enhancement in sports

¹ Pasquini, Nilton Cesar, “Uso de metilfenidato (MFD) por estudantes universitários com intuito de ‘turbinar’ o cérebro”, *Biofar, Rev. Biol. Farm.*, Vol. 9, n. 2, 2013, pp. 107-113. See also Uchoa, G. “Concurseiros apostam em ‘Pílula da Inteligência’ para fortalecer estudos.” *Portal O Dia*, 01 January 2017.

<https://www.portaldia.com/noticias/concursos/concurseiros-apostam-na-pilula-da-inteligencia-para-potencializar-estudos-292350.html>

² Battleday, R. M.; Brem, A. K. “Modafinil for cognitive neuroenhancement in healthy non-sleep-deprived subjects: A systematic review”, *European Neuropsychopharmacology*, Vol. 25, n. 11, 2015, p. 1865-1881. See also Sahakian, Barbara; Labuzetta, J. Nicole. *Bad Moves: How decision making goes wrong, and the ethics of smart drugs*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2013.

³ Barros, Denise; Ortega, Francisco. “Metilfenidato e aprimoramento cognitivo farmacológico: representações sociais de universitários, Saúde e Sociedade”, *Saúde e Sociedade*, Vol. 20, 2011, pp. 350-362.

http://www.scielo.br/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0104-12902011000200008

⁴ Neves, M. L. “Dos remédios controlados ao LSD: as drogas da eficiência,” *Revista Marie Claire*, 6 November 2017.

<https://revistamarieclaire.globo.com/Comportamento/noticia/2017/11/dos-remedios-controlados-ao-lsd-drogas-da-eficiencia.html>

⁵ Brasil (Ministério da Saúde), “Portaria No. 344”, 12 May 1998.

http://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/svs/1998/prt0344_12_05_1998_rep.html

⁶ Sahakian, Barbara; Labuzetta, J. Nicole. *Bad Moves: How decision making goes wrong, and the ethics of smart drugs*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2013.

The use of drugs to enhance physical performance is widespread among athletes.⁷ The Federal Medical Council (*Port.: Conselho Federal de Medicina, CFM*) issued in May 2018 a booklet containing some information concerning the health risks associated with the use of drugs and supplements for the purpose of physical enhancement.⁸ The document was produced in partnership with the Brazilian Society of Sports Medicine (*Port.: Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina do Esporte*), the Brazilian Olympic Committee (*Port.: Comitê Olímpico do Brasil*), the Brazilian Paralympic Committee (*Port.: Comitê Paralímpico Brasileiro*), the Brazilian Football Confederation (*Port.: Confederação Brasileira de Futebol*), and the Brazilian Doping Control Authority (*Port.: Autoridade Brasileira de Controle de Dopagem*). The Brazilian Anti-Doping Code (*Port.: Código Brasileiro Antidopagem*) was created by means of Decree N^o 8.692, from 16 March 2016.⁹

[3] Genetic enhancement by means of IVF and PGD

Strictly speaking, there is not genetic human enhancement in Brazil. The Law N^o 11.105, from March 2005, also known as the Brazilian Biosecurity Law, forbids genetic engineering in human cells for whatever purposes (*Port.: Lei de Biosegurança*, art. No. 6, iii).¹⁰ The Resolution N^o 2.168/2017, issued by CFM in November 2017, also forbids the use of IVF and PGD for non-therapeutic purposes (Part 1, §2, 5). On the other hand, there is currently in Brazil a growing demand for foreign human semen, imported from sperm banks abroad. The Biosecurity Law (art. 5, § 3) prohibits the commercialization of human cells in Brazil. But it does not prohibit the importation of human semen for the purpose of assisted human reproduction in Brazilian fertility clinics. According to a report published by ANVISA in 2017, the importation of sperm samples for assisted human reproduction increased 2.625% in Brazil between 2011 and 2016.¹¹ The demand is so high that the American sperm bank Fairfax Cryobank set up a website in Portuguese for its Brazilian clients.¹² Many American sperm banks enable prospective

⁷ Revista Metrpolis, “No Brasil, 70 atletas so investigados por uso de doping”, November 2018.

<https://www.metropoles.com/esportes/no-brasil-70-atletas-sao-investigados-por-uso-de-doping>

⁸ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Atletas e mdicos ganham guia elaborado por entidades mdicas e esportivas e que ajuda a prevenir casos de doping”, 11 May 2018.

https://portal.cfm.org.br/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=27628:2018-05-11-11-41-54&catid=3

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), *Medicamentos e suplementos nos exerccios e esportes*, Braslia, 2018.

https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/PDF/medicina_esporte.pdf

⁹ Brasil, “Decreto No. 8.692”, 16 March 2016.

<http://www2.camara.leg.br/legin/fed/decret/2016/decreto-8692-16-marco-2016-782563-publicacaooriginal-149755-pe.html>

Autoridade Brasileira Controle de Dopagem (ABCD), *Cdigo Brasileiro de Antidopagem*, 16 March 2016.

[http://www.abcd.gov.br/arquivos/Cdigo_Brasileiro_Antidopagem_Retificado\(1\).pdf](http://www.abcd.gov.br/arquivos/Cdigo_Brasileiro_Antidopagem_Retificado(1).pdf)

¹⁰ Brasil, “Lei No. 11.105”, 24 March 2005.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2004-2006/2005/Lei/L11105.htm

¹¹ Agncia Nacional de Vigilncia Sanitria (ANVISA), “1 Relatório de Amostras Seminais para uso em Reproduo Humana Assistida”, Braslia, 2017.

<http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/4048533/4993603/1%C2%B0+Relat%C3%B3rio+de+Importa%C3%A7%C3%A3o+de+Amostras+Seminais.pdf/Ofa75253-6c73-4b7b-be0c-898f03ccace6>

¹² Fairfax Cryobank: <https://fairfaxcryobank.com/br/>

Alves, Ana Beatriz, “In vitro Fertilization in Brazil Grows 149%”, *Pais&Filhos*, 23 November 2017.

<https://paisefilhos.uol.com.br/quero-engravidar/fertilizacao-in-vitro-cresceu-149-nos-ultimos-cinco-anos-no-brasil/>

clients to choose from a variety of features attributed to the anonymous sperm donor, including, for instance, his highest academic degree, which appears under the label “Education” in the search engine of Fairfax Cryobank’s website. Whether or not this option increases the odds of having a child with above average intelligence is a disputable question, even recognizing that there is strong evidence for the heritability of intelligence.¹³ Although genetic human enhancement is forbidden in Brazil, the importation of human semen from sperm banks that enables prospective parents to choose for “Education” as an indication of intelligence is clearly an example of pursuit of genetic cognitive enhancement in all but name.¹⁴

[4] Prosthetic limbs and microchip implants

High-performance prosthetic limbs have been the object of much research and press coverage worldwide over the last years.¹⁵ The first Cyborg Olympic games, or Cybathlon, took place in 2016 in Zuriq, Switzerland.¹⁶ The Paralympic games, too, have been a showcase for the latest advancements in technologies for prosthetic limbs. The participation of the Brazilian parathlete Alan Oliveira in the 2012 Paralympics, in London, contributed to the public’s awareness that prosthetic limbs have the

¹³ Sniekers, Suzana et al., “Genome-wide association meta-analysis of 78,308 individuals identifies new loci and genes influencing human intelligence”, *Nature Genetics*, Vol. 49, 2017, pp. 1107–1112.

Nature Editorial, “Intelligence test: Modern genetics can rescue the study of intelligence from a history marred by racism”, *Nature*, Vol. 452, 25 May 2017, pp. 385–386.

Shakeshaft, N. et al., “Thinking positively: The genetics of high intelligence”. *Intelligence*, Vol. 48, 2015, pp. 123–132.

Flynn, James. *Intelligence and human progress. The story of what was hidden in our genes*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2013.

Plomin, Robert. “Commentary: Why are children in the same family so different? Non-shared environment three decades later”. *International Journal of Epidemiology*, Vol. 40, 2011, pp. 592–596.

Deary, Ian. et al., “Genetics of intelligence”, *European Journal of Human Genetics*, Vol. 14, No. 6, 2006, pp. 690–700. See also Yong, Ed, “Chinese project probes the genetics of genius. Bid to unravel the secrets of brainpower faces skepticism”. *Nature*, Vol. 497, 2013, pp. 297–299. See also Allhoff, Fritz, “Germ-line genetic enhancement and Rawlsian primary goods”. *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 15, No. 1, 2005, pp. 39-56.

¹⁴ Araujo, Marcelo de, “Editing the genome of human beings CRISPR-Cas9 and the ethics of genetic enhancement”. *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 2017, pp. 24-42.

¹⁵ Reardon, Sara, “The Pentagon’s gamble on brain implants, bionic limbs and combat exoskeletons”, *Nature*, Vol. 522, 2015, pp. 142-144.

<https://www.nature.com/news/the-pentagon-s-gamble-on-brain-implants-bionic-limbs-and-combat-exoskeletons-1.17726>

Turbow, Jason, “Bigger, faster, stronger: will bionic limbs put the olympics to shame?” *Wired*, 8 March 2012. <https://www.wired.com/2012/08/next-gen-prosthetics-and-sports/>

¹⁶ Cybathlon, moving people and Technology. <http://www.cybathlon.ethz.ch/>

Araujo, Marcelo de, “World War I to the age of the cyborg: The surprising history of prosthetic limbs”, *The Conversation*, 6 September 2016.

<https://theconversation.com/world-war-i-to-the-age-of-the-cyborg-the-surprising-history-of-prosthetic-limbs-64451>

potential to enhance human capacities in ways that had not been imagined before.¹⁷ The prosthetic limbs used by Oliveira have been developed by the Icelandic company Össur, which has a branch in Porto Alegre, Brazil.¹⁸ Össur's catalogue of prosthetic limbs, published in Portuguese, includes a range of "bionic" devices with built-in AI (artificial intelligence) such as, for instance, model SYMBIONIC® LEG 3, which is reported to improve substantially the mobility of amputees.¹⁹ However, these devices are very expensive and, for this reason, they remain beyond the reach of most Brazilian amputees. Indeed, even conventional models are unaffordable for many Brazilian individuals who need a prosthetic limb.²⁰ The government Decree (*Port.: Portaria*) No. 403, from 7 May 2015, establishes rules for the "acquisition, reception, handling, and control of prosthetic devices and materials" (*Port.: "aquisição, o recebimento, a utilização e o controle de Órteses, Próteses e Materiais Especiais"*) in public hospitals.²¹ And Law No 9.656, from 3 June 1998²², rules that private health insurance companies are compelled to provide amputees with a range of prosthetic limbs previously determined by the Brazilian Agency for Complementary Health Care (*Port.: Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar, ANS*).²³ In the absence of specific legislation, the commercialization of prosthetic limbs is regulated by the Consumer Protection Code (*Port.: Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law Nº 8.078, from 11 September 1990.)²⁴ There is, however, a 2015 Bill with a proposal for the creation of specific national legislation in this area (*Port.: Projeto de Lei do Senado Nº 17, de 2015*).²⁵ As of October 2018, this Bill has not been enacted into law. Now, it is important to note that none of these documents – press coverage on Paralympic games, Össur's Brazilian catalogue, or the Brazilian legislation for prosthetic limbs – explicitly alludes to HE.

¹⁷ Owen, Gibson, "Paralympics 2012: Oscar Pistorius erupts after Alan Oliveira wins gold", *The Guardian*, 6 September 2016.

<https://www.theguardian.com/sport/2012/sep/03/paralympics-2012-oscar-pistorius-alan-oliveira>

¹⁸ Össur. Life without limitations. <https://www.ossur.com.br/ossur-brazil>

Pessel, Matheus, "Próteses serão melhores que corpo e substituirão quase tudo". *Terra Notícias*, 19 February 2011.

<https://www.terra.com.br/noticias/ciencia/pesquisa/proteses-serao-melhores-que-corpo-e-substituira-quase-tudo,841900beca2da310VgnCLD200000bbceeb0aRCRD.html>

¹⁹ Össur, "Soluções em Próteses: Catálogos", 2017, pp. 6-15.

<http://oc4assets.azurewebsites.net/library/39116>

²⁰ O Globo, "Próteses mais modernas ainda esbarram nos altos preços", 4 November 2017.

<https://blogs.oglobo.globo.com/to-dentro/post/proteses-mais-modernas-ainda-esbarram-nos-altos-precos.html>

²¹ Brasil, "Portaria No. 403", 7 May 2015.

http://bvsmis.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/sas/2015/prt0403_06_05_2015.html

²² Brasil, "Lei No. 9.656", 3 June 1998.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L9656.htm

²³ Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar (ANS), "Como é a cobertura de órteses e próteses pelos planos de saúde?"

http://www.ans.gov.br/aans/index.php?option=com_centraldeatendimento&view=pergunta&resposta=471&historico=18252223

²⁴ Brasil, "Lei No. 8.078", 11 September 1990.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm

²⁵ Brasil, "Projeto de Lei do Senado nº 17", 2015.

<https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/119638>

In the literature on HE, microchip implants are not usually discussed, at any rate not as often as, for instance, *smart drugs* or prosthetic limbs. But to the extent that they may be used for storage of passwords and digital information at large, microchip implants also qualify as HET. Following a concept first introduced by Andy Clark and David Chalmer, microchip implants may be considered “extension of our minds”.²⁶ A man in the state of Minas Gerais, Brazil, is reported to have been the first Brazilian citizen to use a microchip implant to store the passwords of his mobile phone and further electronic devices, in 2018.²⁷ There is currently a Bill with a proposal for the prohibition of microchip implants for the purpose of human identification or GPS localization in Brazil (Bill PL 7561/2014, *Câmara dos Deputados*²⁸, later replaced by Bill Nº 6489/2016²⁹). As of October 2018, this Bill has not been enacted into law.

[5] Aesthetic enhancement through cosmetic surgeries

Plastic surgeries for cosmetic reasons are very common in Brazil. According to the International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery, Brazil has the second highest number of cosmetic surgeries performed every year (see image 1).³⁰ The legislation for the performance of cosmetic surgeries is the same one that applies for medical surgeries in general, namely Law Nº 12.842, from 10 July 2013, which regulates the medical practice in Brazil.³¹ Cosmetic surgeons also have to follow the Brazilian Code of Medical Ethics (*Port.: Código de Ética Médica*).³² There is no specific legislation or professional code of ethics for cosmetic surgeons, that is cosmetic surgeons are bound by the same rules that apply to all physicians and surgeons, except as regards civil liability for the results of a cosmetic surgery. Physicians and surgeons at large are bound to an obligation of *means*, and not the obligation of an actual cure.

²⁶Clark, Andy and David Chalmers, “The extended mind”, *Analysis*, Vol. 58, No. 1, January de 1998, pp. 7-19. See also Levy, Neil, *Neuroethics: Challenges for the 21st Century*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2007, pp. 29-43.

²⁷Jornal da Record, “Mineiro de BH é o primeiro brasileiro a implantar chip na pele que substitui cartões”, 18 May 2015.
<http://recordtv.r7.com/jornal-da-record/videos/mineiro-de-bh-e-o-primeiro-brasileiro-a-implantar-chip-na-pele-que-substitui-cartoes-05102018>

²⁸ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 7561”, 14 May 2014.
<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=615529>
See also Souza, Murilo, “Comissão proíbe implante de chips de identificação em humanos sem autorização”, *Câmara dos Deputados*, 18 August 2017.
<http://www2.camara.leg.br/camaranoticias/noticias/DIREITO-E-JUSTICA/539338-COMISSAO-PROIBE-IMPLANTE-DE-CHIPS-DE-IDENTIFICACAO-EM-HUMANOS-SEM-AUTORIZACAO.html>

²⁹ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 6489”, 2016.
<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=2117288>

³⁰ International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery (ISAPS).
<https://www.isaps.org/medical-professionals/isaps-global-statistics/>

³¹ Brasil, “Lei No. 12.842”, 10 de July 2013.
http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2011-2014/2013/lei/l12842.htm

³² Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), *Código de Ética Médica*, 2009.
<https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/stories/biblioteca/codigo%20de%20etica%20medica.pdf>. See also Silva, Dione Batista Vila-Nova da, and Fabio Xerfan Nahas et al. “A Cirurgia Plástica brasileira e o ‘Código de Ética Médica’”, *Revista Brasileira de Cirurgia Plástica*, 2012, Vol. 27, No. 2, pp.321-324.

They have to perform as best as they can. Plastic surgeons, on the other hand, are bound to an obligation of *results*: they must deliver the results that have been agreed with the patient. The Brazilian Superior Court of Justice (*Port.: Superior Tribunal de Justiça, or STJ*) understands the rules for the performance of cosmetic surgery in this sense, and points out the consumer’s protection code as the actual source for this understanding of the services provided by cosmetic surgeons.

PROCEDURES BY COUNTRY													
ESTIMATED NUMBER OF PLASTIC SURGEONS IN COUNTRY	43,100	6,600	5,500	2,225	1,700	1,634	2,050	2,000	1,200	1,152	950	980	1,002
TOTAL PROCEDURES	WORLD-WIDE TOTALS	USA	BRAZIL	JAPAN	ITALY	MEXICO	RUSSIA	INDIA	TURKEY	GERMANY	FRANCE	COLOMBIA	SPAIN
Surgical Procedures													
Face & Head													
Brow Lift	261,663	28,644	41,140	6,542	6,817	15,932	26,343	4,820	6,528	7,741	2,413	6,909	4,529
Ear Surgery	298,975	16,500	46,530	5,474	12,393	13,056	23,391	18,600	8,760	8,951	8,987	6,223	8,968
Eyelid Surgery	1,347,509	129,624	159,720	106,177	42,483	54,608	118,224	25,780	25,284	58,245	28,681	30,880	31,062
Facelift	427,065	71,148	57,255	7,966	8,517	18,644	41,984	8,680	8,628	15,633	13,756	8,350	8,256
Facial Bone Contouring	109,775	9,636	11,110	4,917	2,159	10,131	7,524	6,640	2,880	2,223	304	3,146	2,745
Fat Grafting-face	596,836	57,222	73,095	7,699	23,664	30,981	44,424	30,100	20,184	22,810	10,783	14,935	13,216
Neck Lift	264,050	33,462	40,810	1,580	5,610	16,291	26,650	7,460	5,832	8,294	7,477	6,125	4,409
Hair Transplantation	135,053	11,418	10,045	1,736	6,426	5,033	841	36,500	11,328	1,002	922	2,940	2,265
Rhinoplasty	786,852	53,130	74,030	23,407	30,855	45,278	54,817	54,180	43,140	15,898	17,746	22,687	17,675
Total Face & Head Procedures	4,227,778	410,784	513,755	165,496	138,924	209,953	344,195	192,760	132,564	140,797	91,067	102,194	93,126

Figure 1: Cosmetic surgeries in Brazil. Source: International Society of Aesthetic Plastic Surgery

This report aims to provide an overview and discussion on these topics from a legal point of view. We focus on the legislation issued over the last 10 years.

Scope and limitations of the report

This report is comprised of two parts. The first part covers the legal developments and an analysis of national legal studies relevant for HE in Brazil. The second part addresses some specific legal issues concerning HET.

2. Part I: Summary of legal developments and an analysis of national legal scholarship

2.1. Legal developments

1. *Have there been attempts or plans to adopt at national level new legislation or set up new regulatory bodies in response to new development and/or increased use of human enhancement technologies³³? Have there been/are there attempts to regulate³⁴ how HETs are designed, set up, commissioned or used?*

Although HE has been pursued in Brazil in a variety of ways, most people seem not to recognize the existence of HE or HET as categories in their own rights. Currently, there is no standard translation for “human enhancement” into Portuguese. In the academic debate, the expression has been usually translated as “aprimoramento humano”, “aperfeiçoamento humano”, or “melhoramento humano”. Although there is already some legislation that regulates the use of performance enhancing drugs in professional sports, or the use of IVF and PGD in fertility clinics, and the use of microchip implants in the private sector, there has not been in Brazil a comprehensive legal debate on HE and HET as such.

In this report, we review some Brazilian laws and regulations that apply to HE and HET, but it is important to notice that these laws and regulations did not arise out of a broader debate on the legal and moral implications of HE and HET. Indeed, these laws and regulations do not even mention “human enhancement”.

2. *Have developments of HETs led to amendments in constitutional or human rights and/or legislation bearing on constitutional or human rights (for example the right to privacy, the right to bodily or mental integrity)? Please identify judgments of the highest national courts (constitutional or supreme courts) that address developments of HET.*

The Law No 11.105, from March 2005, also known as the Brazilian Biosecurity Law (*Port.: Lei de Biosegurança*)³⁵, regulates a specific chapter of the Brazilian Constitution, which was not very informative on the use of biotechnology when the Constitution was enacted in 1988. The recent debate on the use of CRISPR-Cas9, along with the prospect of using this new technology for the purpose of producing better seeds and genetically modified non-human animals for research and for

³³ For what is meant by “new developments and/or increased use of human enhancement technologies” please consult the SIENNA State-of-the-art Review document. To give an example, we are, for instance, interested in the following phenomena currently occurring: the proliferation of cognitive enhancement devices and their easy availability,

- the use of drugs for cognitive enhancement (including administration of the drugs to children),
- recent development of CRISPR-Cas systems,
- the need to protect the augmented body (including technology ON the human body).

We are also interested in the development concerning the more common and established (“traditional”) types of enhancement (e.g. the issues of age limit in cosmetic surgery or the problem of doping) as long as they fit the definition of HET.

³⁴ This could be both to restrict or advance the development or use of such applications.

³⁵ Brasil, “Lei No. 11.105”, 24 March 2005.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_Ato2004-2006/2005/Lei/L11105.htm

human consumption, has been the objection of some discussion in Brazil.³⁶ On the other hand, the use of gene editing technologies (or genetic engineering) on human cells is strictly forbidden by article 6, paragraph iii of the Biosecurity Law:

*“art. No. 6 – it is forbidden: [...] iii – genetic engineering in human germinal cells, human zygote and human embryos”.*³⁷

For the time being, there have not been discussions on a possible amendment to this subsection. Other aspects of human enhancement, which relate, for instance, to the use of drugs, prosthetic devices, or microchip implants, have not been extensively debated from a constitutional perspective, neither have they entailed a debate concerning human rights issues.

2.2. Legal scholarship

The following search terms were used:

Search terms in English	Search terms in Portuguese
1. Human enhancement	<i>Aprimoramento humano; aperfeiçoamento humano; melhoramento humano</i>
2. Non-therapeutic human enhancement ³⁸	<i>Melhoramento não-terapêutico</i>
3. (Human) Enhancement technologies	<i>Tecnologias para aprimoramento humano</i>
4. Non-therapeutic services	<i>Serviços não-terapêuticos</i>
5. Non-therapeutic medical services (sic!)	<i>Serviços médicos não-terapêuticos</i>
6. Non-medical health devices	<i>Aparelhos médicos para fins não-terapêuticos</i>

³⁶ Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança (CTNBIO), “Resolução Normativa No. 16”, 15 January 2018.
http://ctnbio.mcti.gov.br/resolucoes-normativas/-/asset_publisher/OgW431Rs9dQ6/content/resolucao-normativa-n%C2%BA-16-de-15-de-janeiro-de-2018;jsessionid=0DC3D2823FBBA6DE845927FE0B754BDD.rima?redirect=http%3A%2F%2Fctnbio.mcti.gov.br%2Fresolucoes-normativas%3Bjsessionid%3D0DC3D2823FBBA6DE845927FE0B754BDD.rima%3Fp_id%3D101_INSTANCE_OgW431Rs9dQ6%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolu mn-2%26p_p_col_count%3D3

Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação, Comissão Técnica Nacional de Biossegurança (CTNBIO), Resolução No. 18, 23 March 2018.
http://ctnbio.mcti.gov.br/resolucoes-normativas/-/asset_publisher/OgW431Rs9dQ6/content/resolucao-n%C2%BA-18-de-23-de-marco-de-2018;jsessionid=F574C62F718C6C84A52615351C86B5A2.rima

³⁷ Brasil, “Lei No. 11.105”, 24 March 2005.
http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2004-2006/2005/lei/l11105.html

³⁸ Official Journal of the European Union, “Nanoscience and Nanotechnology”, 28 September 2018.
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:C:2006:306E:0426:0429:ES:PDF>

7. Lifestyle medical services	<i>Serviços médicos para estilo de vida</i>
8. “Legislation” + “Brazil” + “Enhancement”	<i>“Legislação” + “Brasil” “aprimoramento” (or “melhoramento” or “aperfeiçoamento”)</i>

Search Results in Google (as of November 2018):

<i>Aprimoramento humano; aperfeiçoamento humano; melhoramento humano</i>	4.310 search results. Most entries cover usages that are not relevant for the project. Search results that are relevant for the project relate mostly to ethical and philosophical discussion on human enhancement. Search results related to legal content has not been found.
<i>Melhoramento não-terapêutico</i>	1 search result in a master thesis in philosophy (PDF file).
<i>Tecnologias para aprimoramento humano</i>	3 search results. The first search results refers to an article in Portuguese about the SIENNA Project.
<i>Serviços não-terapêuticos</i>	0 search result
<i>Serviços medicos não-terapêuticos</i>	0 search result
<i>Aparelhos médicos para fins não- terapêuticos</i>	0 search result
<i>Serviços médicos para estilo de vida</i>	0 search result
<i>“Legislação” + “Brasil” “aprimoramento” (or “melhoramento” or “aperfeiçoamento”)</i>	3.590 search results. Most entries cover usages that are not relevant for the project. The first search result refers to an article in Portuguese about the SIENNA Project.

3. Part II: Analysis of specific legal issues

3.1. Terminology and legal demarcations

1. *Does the domestic law in your country provide a legal definition of “health” or the state of “health”? If yes, please quote the relevant source. Has the question of the definition of “health” been addressed in the case law?*

The Brazilian Constitution, enacted in 1998 (henceforth *Constitution*),³⁹ established that every citizen has a right to health, and that the government has a duty to provide citizens with the means to good health:

TITLE VIII
The Social Order
CHAPTER I
General Provision
Article 193.
The social order is based on the primacy of work and aimed at social well-being and justice.
CHAPTER II
Social Welfare
SECTION I
General Provisions
[...]
SECTION II
Health
Article 196.
Health is a right of all and a duty of the State and shall be guaranteed by means of social and economic policies aimed at reducing the risk of illness and other hazards and at the universal and equal access to actions and services for its promotion, protection and recovery.
Article 197.
Health actions and services are of public importance, and it is incumbent upon the Government to provide, in accordance with the law, for their regulation, supervision and control, and they shall be carried out directly or by third parties and also by individuals or private legal entities.⁴⁰

In order to protect the basic right to health, the Brazilian government created in 1990 the Unified Health System (*Port.: Sistema Único de Saúde, SUS*), which follows three basic principles: universality of health care, equal access to the health care system, and integral care.⁴¹ The establishment of SUS has been generally regarded as an important step towards the democratization of the health care system in Brazil. Previous to the creation of SUS, “health” was legally conceived as a condition of “non-disease”. The main function of the health care system, then, was to treat diseases rather than taking measures for the prevention of diseases in the first place. The Constitution and the creation of SUS changed this understanding of the concept of health. The concept of health, as it has been promoted now by SUS, encompasses also the concept of quality of life of the population as a whole, which in its

³⁹ Brasil, “Constitution”, 1988.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm

⁴⁰ Brasil, “Constitution”, 1988.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm

⁴¹ Brasil, Ministério da Saúde, Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS).

<http://portalms.saude.gov.br/sistema-unico-de-saude> See also Löwy, Ilana. “Visible Disasters: Fetopathology in Brazil”, *Tangled Diagnoses: Prenatal Testing, Women, and Risk*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago and London, 2018, pp. 108-146.

turn implies access to sanitation, employment, education, healthy environment, housing, food, and leisure.⁴²

This enlargement of the concept of health, though, as inclusive as it sounds, came with a price. It is often up to judges to decide whether or not a given claim should be satisfied as a matter of right. If a citizen has, for instance, a rare disease, which can only be treated by means of an expensive treatment, the citizen, according to the Constitution, has a legitimate claim to the relevant treatment as a matter of right. The medicine Solaris (also known as Eculizumab), for instance, is reported to be one of the most expensive drugs in the world. In 2012, a Brazilian patient required the medicine and, as he did not obtain the drug from the government, he filed a suit against the government, in the state of São Paulo, for the violation of his basic right to health.⁴³ A court order ruled that the state had, indeed, to provide the patient with the drug. This judicial decision, then, set a precedent for other similar cases, even in regions of Brazil where the acquisition of the drug may represent a substantial burden on the budget allotted for the local health care system. In some cases, a court can also decide that a private health insurance company must provide a patient with expensive treatments, which are not covered by the insurance policy. Recently, for instance, a patient with Alzheimer's disease was denied treatment with Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) to prevent the progressive loss of his cognitive functions. The patient filed a suit against his health insurance company, which had then to comply with a court order to the benefit of the patient.⁴⁴ In the attempt to protect the basic right to health, some courts have even granted patients with unproven cancer treatment.⁴⁵

The authors of this report speculate that, in the future, as HET become widespread and more reliable, and as the line between treatment and enhancement becomes further blurred, the current legal foundations of Brazilian health care system might well afford judges the power to grant citizens access to HET as a matter of basic right. The Article 196 of the Constitution, quoted above, affirms that it is incumbent upon the government to provide services for the “promotion, protection and recovery” of the health of the population. Depending on the way the word “promotion” (*Port.: promoção*) is interpreted, HE might well be understood as a means for the “promotion” of human health.

⁴² Ministério da Saúde, Sistema Único de Saúde SUS, “Princípios e Conquistas”, 2000, p. 5.
http://bvsm.sau.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/sus_principios.pdf

⁴³ Segatto, Cristiane, “O paciente de 800 mil reais”, *Revista Época*, 16 March 2012.
<http://revistaepoca.globo.com/tempo/noticia/2012/03/o-paciente-de-r-800-mil.html>

Permuy, Pedro, “Campanhas em família para garota receber remédio que custa R \$ 88 mil por mês no ES”, *G1 Globo*, 6 June 2017.

<https://g1.globo.com/espírito-santo/noticia/familia-faz-campanha-para-menina-receber-remedio-que-custa-r-88-mil-por-mes-no-es.ghtml>

⁴⁴ De Oliveira, Rinaldo, “Cirurgia de médicos brasileiros reverte a doença de Alzheimer: Memória voltando”, *Pazes*, 2 November 2017.

<https://www.revistapazes.com/cirurgia-de-medico-brasileiro-reverte-alzheimer-memoria-voltando>

G1 Globo, “Neurocirurgia fala sobre cirurgia para retardar a progressão da doença de Alzheimer”.

<http://g1.globo.com/pb/paraiba/jpb-1edicao/videos/v/neurocirurgiao-fala-sobre-cirurgia-para-frear-a-evolucao-do-alzheimer/4707938/>

⁴⁵ Ledford, Heidi, “Brazilian courts tussle over unproven cancer treatment”, *Nature*, 24 November 2017.
<https://www.nature.com/news/brazilian-courts-tussle-over-unproven-cancer-treatment-1.18864>

2. What are the basic legal terms and demarcations used nationally that should be taken into consideration in the discussion on the regulation of HET?⁴⁶ Please consider the following dichotomies: medical v. non-medical, treatment v. enhancement, therapeutic v. non-therapeutic, natural v. non-natural. Are there any other potentially relevant legal demarcations or distinctions? Please provide a list of terms in the national language and an English translation (in case of doubt, please briefly explain the nature or source of doubts).

The basic legal terms that should be taken into consideration for a discussion on HET regulations in Brazil are the following:

English	Portuguese
Dignity	<i>Dignidade</i>
Autonomy	<i>Autonomia</i>
Right to health	<i>Direito à Saúde</i>
Informed consent	<i>Consentimento Informado</i> or <i>Consentimento Esclarecido</i>
“promotion, protection and recovery” of health, as stated in Article 190 of the Constitution	<i>“promoção, proteção e recuperação” da saúde</i>
Harm	<i>Dano</i> or <i>Lesão</i>
Therapy	<i>Terapia</i>
Treatment	<i>Tratamento</i>

Currently, there is hardly any legal discussion on HE in Brazil. HE issues have not been addressed by legislators either. The discussion on HE and HET has been pursued mostly by philosophers.⁴⁷

⁴⁶ Please consult the SIENNA State of the Art deliverable concerning the main relevant demarcations in the field of HET.

⁴⁷ See for instance Oliveira, Nythamar de, “Moral reasoning in metaethics, bioethics, and neuroethics: On Ritalin, Adderall, and the normative challenges of cognitive enhancement”, *Ethic@*, Vol. 15, 2016, pp. 343-368. Azevedo, Marco A. O. “The misfortunes of moral enhancement”, *The journal of medicine and philosophy*, Vol. 41, pp. 461-479, 2016. Azevedo, Marco A. O. “Pode o melhoramento humano ser aceito como um dos objetivos da medicina?” *Barbarói (UNISC. Online)*, Vol. 44, pp. 290-303, 2015. Dall’Agnol, Darlei, “Princípios bioéticos e melhoramento cognitivo”, *Thaumazein*, Vol. 10, pp. 17-28, 2017. Dall’Agnol, Darlei. “Neurobioética e políticas públicas para melhoramento cognitivo”, in Crisp, Roger, and Darlei Dall’Agnol, and Julian Savulescu, and Milene Tonetto (eds.), in *Ética aplicada e políticas públicas*, Florianópolis, UFSC Editora, 2018, pp. 77-98. Pinzani, Alessandro. “Há um dever de ser um deus? Sobre o imperativo moral de ter uma mente bilhante num corpo perfeito”, in Crisp, Roger, and Darlei Dall’Agnol, and Julian Savulescu, and Milene Tonetto (eds.), in *Ética aplicada e políticas públicas*, Florianópolis, UFSC Editora, 2018, p. 119-136. Nahra, Cinra, “Políticas públicas para o aprimoramento do altruísmo”, in Crisp, Roger, and Darlei Dall’Agnol, and Julian Savulescu, and Milene Tonetto (eds.), in *Ética aplicada e políticas públicas*, Florianópolis, UFSC Editora, 2018, pp. 61-76. Araujo, Marcelo de, and Patricia Fachin, “Passado e presente do debate sobre a ética do aprimoramento cognitivo no Brasil: da ‘mocidade pervitínica’ à ‘geração Ritalina’”, in Crisp, Roger, and Darlei Dall’Agnol, and Julian Savulescu, and Milene Tonetto (eds.), in *Ética aplicada e políticas públicas*, Editora UFSC, Florianópolis, 2018, pp. 99-118. Araujo, Marcelo de, “A ética do aprimoramento cognitivo: Efeito Flynn e a falácia dos talentos naturais”, *Ethic@*, 2017, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 1-14. Araujo, Marcelo de, “Próteses na cultura do período

It has been pointed out in the previous section of this report that the basic right to health, protected in Article 196 of the Constitution, entails a duty, incumbent upon the government, to “promote” the health of the population. (Article 196 uses the noun “promoção” rather than the verb “promover”. But this does not represent a relevant semantic distinction). The word “treatment” is usually employed to refer to a procedure or intervention in a person whose health is compromised by an illness or disorder. On the other hand, the word “promotion” might be used to refer to a procedure or intervention in a *healthy* person in the attempt to make him or her even *healthier*. If this understanding of “promotion” is deemed acceptable from a constitutional point of view, then it might possibly be alleged that the government has not only a duty to provide the population with “treatment”, but also a duty to provide HET to the extent, of course, that HET prove instrumental to the purpose of “promoting” the health of the population. This understanding of “promotion”, and its implication to a legal debate on HET, might entail an enormous economic burden for SUS, which currently – at least in many regions of Brazil – can hardly provide the population with basic health care. This broader understanding of “promotion” of the health of the population might also be interpreted as a form of state sponsored eugenics policy. The Code of Ethics of the following professional associations prohibits eugenic practices:

- Brazilian Council of Biology (*Port.: Conselho Federal de Biologia, CFBio*, Chapter 5, art. 22).⁴⁸
- Brazilian Federal Council of Biomedicine (*Port.: Conselho Federal de Biomedicina, CFBM*, Chapter 3, art. 5, xi).⁴⁹
- Brazilian Federal Council of Medicine (*Port.: Conselho Federal de Medicina, CFM*, Chapter 3, art. 15, §2 and Chapter 12 art. 99. It also forbids non-therapeutic gene editing and germline modification for whatever purposes, Chapter 3, art. 16).⁵⁰
- *Brazilian Federal Council of Pharmacy (Port.: Conselho Federal de Farmácia, CFF*, Chapter 4, art. 14, i and Annex 3, art 9, ii).⁵¹

The word “eugenics” (*Port.: eugenia*) has a derogatory connotation in Portuguese as Brazil pursued “eugenic policies” in the first half of twentieth century in the attempt to increase the number of white

entreguerras: Uma investigação sobre as origens do debate filosófico sobre *aprimoramento humano*”, *Prometeus*, Vol. 23, 2017. pp. 267-298. Araujo, Marcelo, “Editing the genome of human beings CRISPR-Cas9 and the ethics of genetic enhancement”, *Journal of Evolution and Technology*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 2017, pp. 24-42. Araujo, Marcelo de, “World War I to the age of the cyborg: the surprising history of prosthetic limbs”, *The Conversation*, 6 September 2016. <https://theconversation.com/world-war-i-to-the-age-of-the-cyborg-the-surprising-history-of-prosthetic-limbs-64451>

⁴⁸ Conselho Federal de Biologia (CFBIO), “Código de Ética do Profissional Biólogo”.

<http://www.cfbio.gov.br/artigos/RESOLUCAO-N%C2%BA-2-DE-5-DE-MARCO-DE-2002>

⁴⁹ Conselho Federal de Biomedicina (CFBM), “Código de Ética do Profissional Biomédico”.

<http://cfbm.gov.br/legislacao/codigo-de-etica-da-profissao-de-biomedico/>

⁵⁰ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Código de Ética Médica”.

<https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/stories/biblioteca/codigo%20de%20etica%20medica.pdf>

⁵¹ Conselho Federal de Farmácia (CFF), “Código de Ética da Profissão Farmacêutica”.

<http://www.cff.org.br/userfiles/file/Código%20de%20Etica%2003fev2014.pdf>

people in the population.⁵² For this reason, the word “eugenics” is still associated with the deliberate attempt to change the phenotypic profile of the population so as to favor human features that some people (out of prejudice) consider better than other features (having white skin rather than black skin, having blue eyes rather than dark eyes, etc.). The use of the word “eugenics” as it has been employed, for instance, by Nicholas Agar in the 2004 book *Liberal eugenics: In defence of human enhancement*, is not current in the Portuguese language outside of the academic debate on human enhancement.⁵³

On the other hand, even if it is agreed that the government does not have a duty to pursue the “promotion” of the health by promoting the HE of the population, as it would be a type of eugenics policy, it might still be alleged that private citizens have the right to pursue the enhancement of their own cognitive or physical capacities, as long as they do not *harm* their fellow citizens. The attempt to prevent citizens from enhancing themselves, as long as they have given their *informed consent* to the enhancement procedure, would represent a threat to their *autonomy* and *dignity*. This means that they should not be prohibited from acquiring medical drugs for non-therapeutic purposes as long as they are aware of the risks involved.⁵⁴ Yet, it is not clear whether this argument would be promptly accepted in the Brazilian Supreme Court (*Port.: Supremo Tribunal Federal, STF*). Reference to autonomy and dignity, for instance, has not been enough to grant women the right to abortion as it became apparent after a public hearing in August 2018.⁵⁵

3. What criteria are used to classify services, devices and products according to those categories?

The criteria for classifying the services, devices, and products are established by the relevant legislation and, as the case may be, by resolutions and guidelines issued by the relevant bodies of the government.

Medical services are regulated and classified by Law No. 12.842, from 10 July 2013, which regulates the medical practice in Brazil.⁵⁶ Even though cosmetic surgery is widely performed in Brazil, there has

⁵² Stepan, Nancy Leys, “Eugenics in Brazil, 1917-1940”, in Mark B. Adams (ed.), *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Oxford University Press, Oxford/New York, 1990, pp. 110-152. See also Hochman, Gilberto, and Nísia Trindade Lima, Macos Chor Maio, “The path of eugenics in Brazil: Dilemmas of miscegenation”, in Alison Bashford, Philippa Levine (eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of the History of Eugenics*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2010, pp. 493-510. See also Walsh, Sarah, “The executioner’s shadow: Coerced sterilization and the creation of ‘Latin’ eugenics in Chile”, *History of Science*, pp. 1-23 (doi/10.1177/0073275318755533).

⁵³ Agar, Nicholas, *Liberal eugenics: In defence of human enhancement*, Blackwell, Oxford, 2004.

⁵⁴ Lanigan, Jessica F., *Pharmaceutical freedom: Why patients have a right to self-medicate*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2017. For a discussion of concepts such as dignity, autonomy, right to health, and informed consent in the context of Brazilian law, see Lobo, Torres Ricardo, and Eduardo Kataoka Takemi, and Flavio Galdino, *Dicionário de Termos Jurídicos*, Rio de Janeiro, Elsevier, 2011.

⁵⁵ Supremo Tribunal Federal (STF), “Relatora encerra audiência pública sobre descriminalização do aborto”, *Notícias STF*, 6 August 2018. See also Andreoni, Manuela and Ernesto Londoño, “Brazil’s Supreme Court Considers decriminalizing abortion”, *The New York Times*, 3 August 2018.

<https://www.nytimes.com/2018/08/03/world/americas/brazil-abortion-supreme-court.html>

⁵⁶ Brasil, “Lei No. 12.842”, 10 July 2013.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2013/lei/l12842.htm

not been a debate on the use medical procedures and medical devices for non-therapeutic purposes, that is medical devices, as defined by Law No. 12.842, from 10 July 2013, are defined in terms of treatment.

The CFM, as mentioned above, has its own Code of Ethics.⁵⁷ Moreover, CFM regularly updates its rules concerning, for instance, the use of IVF and PGD for assisted human reproduction, or the use of robots and AI for the performance of surgeries and diagnoses. Some of its resolutions include, for instance, the following documents:

- Resolution CFM Nº 2.178/2017 (*Port.: Resolução CFM Nº 2.178/2017*): This document establishes general guidelines for the use of mobile phone apps that offer health consulting services.⁵⁸
- CFM-commissioned report. CFM Nº 31/2017 – Opinion CFM Nº 41/2017(*Port.: Processo-Consulta CFM Nº 31/2017 – Parecer CFM Nº 41/2017*): This report assesses the ethics of using robot Da Vinci Surgical System (built and sold by the American company Intuitive Surgical) for thyroidectomy. The report suggests that it would be unethical to employ in Brazil a procedure that has not been approved in its country of origin (The United States of America).⁵⁹
- Resolution CFM Nº 2.107/2014 (*Resolução CFM Nº 2.107/2014*): This document defines and rules the practice of teleradiology in Brazil.⁶⁰
- Resolution CFM Nº 1.643/2002 (*Resolução CFM Nº 1.643/2002*): This document defines and rules the use of technologies for telemedicine in Brazil.⁶¹
- Resolution Nº 2.168/2017, from November 2017(*Port.: Resolução Nº 2.168/2017*): This document establishes rules for assisted human reproduction in Brazil. IVF and PGD cannot be used to determine human features unrelated to illnesses or genetic disorders. Features such as sex or eye colours cannot be chosen by prospective parents or clinicians.

Medical devices and products are classified and regulated by ANVISA.⁶² In 2011 ANVISA published, in partnership with the Brazilian Agency for Industrial Development (*Port.: Agência Brasileira de Desenvolvimento Industrial, ABDI*) and the Brazilian Micro and Small Enterprises' Support Service

⁵⁷ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Código de Ética Médica”.

<https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/stories/biblioteca/codigo%20de%20etica%20medica.pdf>

⁵⁸ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No. 2.178”, 2017.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2178>

⁵⁹ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Parecer CFM No. 41”, 2017.

https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/arquivos/pareceres/BR/2017/41_2017.pdf

⁶⁰ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No. 2.107”, 2014.

http://www.portalmedico.org.br/resolucoes/CFM/2014/2107_2014.pdf

⁶¹ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No. 1.643”, 2002.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2002/1643>

⁶² Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Regularização de Produtos - Produtos para Saúde”.

<http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/registros-e-autorizacoes/produtos-para-a-saude/produtos/equipamentos-medicos>

See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Saúde, Registros e Autorizações de Produtos para Saúde”.

<http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/registros-e-autorizacoes/produtos-para-a-saude>

(Port.: *Serviço Brasileiro de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas, SEBRAE*), a handbook with guidelines for the development, classification, and certification of medical equipment and medical devices in Brazil. The publication is called Handbook of Sanitary Legislation for Medical Devices (Port.: *Compendio da Legislação Sanitária de Dispositivos Médicos*).⁶³ Although the Handbook also covers issues related to the development and commercialization of prosthetic limbs, there is also a Bill, from 2015, with a proposal for legislation on this particular topic in Brazil (Port.: *Projeto de Lei do Senado n° 17, de 2015*). As of October 2018 the Bill has not been enacted into law.⁶⁴

4.2 Right to integrity of the person, legal permissibility of non-therapeutic services on the human body

1. *Does the domestic law recognize the right to (physical and/or mental) integrity of the person? If yes, please provide a relevant citation. What are the limits to this right? Please provide examples. What criteria and values are considered to set those limits?*

The Constitution establishes, in Article No. 5, a whole range of personal rights that also include protections related to physical and mental integrity. The Brazilian Civil Code (Port.: *Código Civil*, Law N° 10.406, from 10 January 2002),⁶⁵ also contains a chapter on rights related to personal integrity. These rights aim at the protection of an individual's life, integrity, freedom, sociability, honour, privacy, authorship, and image. Article 5 of the Constitution contains 78 subsections, the first six of which read as follow:

⁶³ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), "Anvisa lança publicação que reúne legislação de produtos para saúde", 20 May 2011.

<http://www.brasil.gov.br/noticias/saude/2011/05/anvisa-lanca-publicacao-que-reune-legislacao-de-produtos-para-saude> See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), "Compendio da Legislação Sanitária de Dispositivos Médicos", http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/resultado-de-busca?p_p_id=101&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=maximized&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_count=1&_101_struts_action=/asset_publisher/view_content&_101_assetEntryId=265165&_101_type=document The Handbook is available at:

<http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/documents/33912/264673/Compendio+da+legisla%C3%A7%C3%A3o+sanit%C3%A1ria+de+Dispositivos+M%C3%A9dicos.pdf/fafed8bb-2551-4249-a18b-82123236614c?version=1.2&download=true>

⁶⁴ Brasil, "Projeto de Lei do Senado n° 17", 2015.

<https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/119638> See also Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar (ANS) and Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), "Grupo de Trabalho, Externo de Órteses, Próteses e Materiais Especiais (GTE OPME)", 2016.

http://www.ans.gov.br/images/stories/Participacao_da_sociedade/2016_gt_opme/gt-opme-relatoriointegral.pdf See also Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar (ANS), "Como é a cobertura de órteses e próteses pelos planos de saúde?"

http://www.ans.gov.br/aans/index.php?option=com_centraldeatendimento&view=pergunta&resposta=471&historico=18252223 See also Brasil, Ministério da Saúde, "Portaria No. 403", 7 May 2015.

http://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/sas/2015/prt0403_06_05_2015.html

⁶⁵ Brasil, "Código Civil Brasileiro. Lei No. 10.406", 10 January 2002.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm

TITLE II
Fundamental Rights and Guarantees
CHAPTER I
Individual and Collective Rights and Duties

Article No. 5. All persons are equal before the law, without any distinction whatsoever, Brazilians and foreigners residing in the country being ensured of inviolability of the right to life, to liberty, to equality, to security and to property, on the following terms:

- I - men and women have equal rights and duties under the terms of this Constitution;
- II - no one shall be obliged to do or refrain from doing something except by virtue of law;
- III - no one shall be submitted to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment;
- IV - the expression of thought is free, and anonymity is forbidden;
- V - the right of reply is ensured, in proportion to the offense, as well as compensation for property or moral damages or for damages to the image;
- VI – freedom of conscience and of belief is inviolable, the free exercise of religious cults being ensured and, under the terms of the law, the protection of places of worship and their rites being guaranteed;

The limit of a right that protects the physical and mental integrity of the person is, often, another right, or group of rights, that also protect the physical and mental integrity of the person. “Freedom of conscience”, for instance, is protected by the Constitution, but this right cannot be evoked to justify unfair treatment towards women, as “men and women have equal rights and duties under the terms of this Constitution”. When these rights clash with one another, it is up to judges, and ultimately the Brazilian Supreme Court (*Port.: Supremo Tribunal Federal, STF*) to settle the case. In section 3.1.1 above, for instance, we have alluded to a court decision that found that a specific man had the right to receive from the government a very costly treatment on the grounds of his basic right to health. At the outset of the Constitution the “dignity of the person” is enshrined as one of its most fundamental values:

TITLE I
Fundamental Principles
Article 1.
[...]
III – the dignity of the human person;⁶⁶

But, again, it is up to the judiciary branch to decide what ultimately counts or, as the case may be, what does not count, as a threat to the basic value of “the dignity of the human person.”

2. *How is the legality of enhancement procedures (understood as non-therapeutic interventions in the human body) established?*

⁶⁶ See also Junqueira, Antonio, “Caracterização jurídica da dignidade da pessoa humana”, *Revisão Trimestral do Direito Civil - RTDC*, No. 9, 2002.

“Human enhancement” and “enhancement procedures” are not recognised per se in Brazilian law. Some specific procedures that might be considered as examples of “enhancement procedures” are, indeed, regulated by law, even though the expression “enhancement”, or one of its counterpart expressions in Portuguese, do not occur in the legal document. The best example in this regard is cosmetic surgery. The rules concerning the performance of cosmetic surgeries, as stated in the introduction of this report, are the same rules that also regulate the performance of medical surgeries in general, that is there is no specific legislation or professional code of ethics for cosmetic surgeons, as cosmetic surgeons are bound by the same rules that apply to all physicians and surgeons, except for they have an obligation of results, and not only an obligation of means. (They have to deliver the results agreed with the patient previous to the performance of the surgery). The professional code of ethics for cosmetic surgeons is the same one that applies to other physicians (*Port.: médico*). Procedures for the purpose of physical enhancement among athletes are regulated by the Brazilian Anti-Doping Code (*Port.: Código Brasileiro Antidopagem*), created by means of Decree No. 8.692, from 16 March 2016.⁶⁷ Cognitive enhancement by means of drugs such as modafinil or methylphenidate is not forbidden per se, but the commercialization of these drugs without an appropriate medical prescription is forbidden by Decree (*Port.: Portaria*) No. 344, from 12 May 1998 entitled Technical Regulation on Substances and Medicinal Products subject to Special Control. (*Port.: Regulamento Técnico sobre Substâncias e Medicamentos Sujeitos a Controle Especial*).⁶⁸ Genetic human enhancement is forbidden by the Biosecurity Law and, more specifically, by Resolution Nº 2.168/2017, which CFM issued in November 2017:

5. AR [sc. Assisted Reproduction] techniques cannot be applied with the intention of selecting the sex (presence or absence of Y chromosome) or any other biological feature of the future child, except to avoid possible descending diseases.⁶⁹

As to human enhancement procedures by means of prosthetic limbs, or electronic devices inserted into the human body, it is less clear. If an individual has to wear a prosthetic limb because he or she suffered an accident, or was born with a missing or deformed limb, it is up to them to decide which kind of prosthetic limb they intend to wear. Brazilian law does not prohibit the use of prosthetic limbs that, at least in principle, might enable an amputee to perform better (run faster, walk longer distances, carry heavier objects, etc) than he or she would with a natural limb. On the other hand, a surgeon cannot amputate a limb for non-therapeutic reasons, even if the patient gives his or her consent to perform the procedure. Such a procedure would violate the Article 2 of Law No. 12.842⁷⁰,

⁶⁷ Brasil, “Decreto No. 8.692”, 16 March 2016.

<http://www2.camara.leg.br/legin/fed/decret/2016/decreto-8692-16-marco-2016-782563-publicacaooriginal-149755-pe.html> See also Autoridade Brasileira Controle de Dopagem (ABCD), “Código Brasileiro de Antidopagem”, 16 March 2016.

[http://www.abcd.gov.br/arquivos/Cdigo_Brasileiro_Antidopagem_Retificado\(1\).pdf](http://www.abcd.gov.br/arquivos/Cdigo_Brasileiro_Antidopagem_Retificado(1).pdf)

⁶⁸ Brasil, “Portaria No. 344”, 12 May 1998.

http://bvsms.saude.gov.br/bvs/saudelegis/svs/1998/prt0344_12_05_1998_rep.html

⁶⁹ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolução CFM No. 2.168”, 2017.

<https://sistemas.cfm.org.br/normas/visualizar/resolucoes/BR/2017/2168>

⁷⁰ Brasil, “Lei No. 12.842”, 10 July 2013.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2013/lei/l12842.htm

from 10 July 2013, which as explained earlier, regulates the medical practice in Brazil. Article 2 defines the actions of a medical doctor in terms of treatment:

- I - promotion, protection and recovery of health;
- II - prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases;
- III - rehabilitation of the sick and disabled.

Such a procedure (amputating one's limb with one's consent but for non therapeutic reasons) might also be interpreted as a violation of Article 13 of the Brazilian Civil Code (*Código Civil*, Law Nº 10.406, from 10 January 2002):

Art. 13. Except for medical exigency, the act of disposing of one's own body, when importing **permanent diminution of the physical integrity**, or contrary to the good customs, is forbidden. (Emphasis added)

3. *Are there limits to what non-therapeutic procedures can be performed on a human body? What criteria are used to establish those limits? What is the role of consent? Does the national law, case-law or legal doctrine provide any guidance on how risks and benefits of non-therapeutic procedures should be weighed and/or what is the acceptable level of risk in those cases?*

Non-therapeutic procedures performed by non-medical professionals

Some non-therapeutic procedures, such as for instance tattooing, piercing, or microchip implants, are not performed by physicians or surgeons. (Whether or not tattooing and piercing qualify as human cosmetic enhancement is a moot question, which will not be addressed here). There is currently no specific nationwide legislation that regulates tattooing and piercing services. On the other hand, there are guidelines, issued by ANVISA, that have been devised to help legislators to regulate this matter. These guidelines, however, do not have the force of law.⁷¹ There is also a Bill from 2015 for the regulation of tattooing and piercing services in Brazil.⁷² Both documents (the ANVISA guidelines and the Bill from 2015) require informed consent as a condition for offering tattooing and piercing services. In the absence of a nationwide legislation, some states and municipalities have regulated the matter on a local level.⁷³

⁷¹ Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), "Referência técnica para o funcionamento dos serviços de tatuagem e piercing (Versão 1.1)".

http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/resultado-de-busca?p_p_id=101&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=maximized&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_count=1&_101_struts_action=%2Fasset_publisher%2Fview_content&_101_assetEntryId=419216&_101_type=document

⁷² Brasil, "Projeto de Lei No. 2065", 2015.

http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/prop_mostrarintegra?codteor=1352624

⁷³ Brasil, "Lei No. 7926", 27 March 2018.

<https://gov-rj.jusbrasil.com.br/legislacao/561225419/lei-7926-27-marco-2018-rio-de-janeiro-rj> See also

As for microchip implants in human beings, there is currently no legislation that addresses this matter. There is, on the other hand, a Bill from 2016 with a proposal for specific legislation on this matter, namely Bill No. 6489/2016.⁷⁴ (This Bill replaces a previous Bill on the same topic, namely Bill PL 7561/2014).⁷⁵ The current Bill proposes the prohibition of microchip implants for the purpose of human identification or GPS localization in Brazil (Bill PL 7561/2014, *Câmara dos Deputados*⁷⁶, later replaced by Bill Nº 6489/2016⁷⁷). This would prevent, for instance, employers from constantly monitoring the localization of their employees. As of October 2018, though, this Bill has not been enacted into law.

Non-therapeutic procedures performed by medical professionals

Strictly speaking, physicians are not allowed to perform non-therapeutic procedures on the body of a patient, as the medical profession itself is defined in terms of its capacity to promote the “treatment” and “rehabilitation” of individuals, as stated in the text of Law Nº 12.842, from 10 July 2013, which regulates the medical practice in Brazil:

Art. No. 2

The object of the physician’s action is the health of the human being and of the human communities, for the benefit of which the physician must act with the utmost zeal, to the best of his or her professional capacity and without discrimination of any nature.

Single paragraph. The physician will develop his or her professional actions in the field of health care to:

- I - promotion, protection and recovery of health;
- II - prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases;

Brasil, “Lei No. 7970”, 21 May 2018.

<https://gov-rj.jusbrasil.com.br/legislacao/581017979/lei-7970-18-rio-de-janeiro-rj>

⁷⁴ Brazil, “Projeto de Lei No. 6489”, 2016.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=2117288>

⁷⁵ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 7561”, 14 May 2014.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=615529>. See also Souza, Murilo, “Comissão proíbe implante de chips de identificação em humanos sem autorização”, *Câmara dos Deputados Notícias*, 18 August 2017, <http://www2.camara.leg.br/camaranoticias/noticias/DIREITO-E-JUSTICA/539338-COMISSAO-PROIBE-IMPLANTE-DE-CHIPS-DE-IDENTIFICACAO-EM-HUMANOS-SEM-AUTORIZACAO.html> See also Neves, Maria, “Projeto veda implantação de mecanismos de rastreamento em humanos”, *Câmara dos Deputados Notícias*, 29 October 2014, <http://www2.camara.leg.br/camaranoticias/noticias/DIREITO-E-JUSTICA/476690-PROJETO-VEDA-IMPLANTACAO-DE-MECANISMOS-DE-RASTREAMENTO-EM-HUMANOS.html>

⁷⁶ Brasil, “Projeto de Lei No. 7561”, 14 May 2014.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=615529>

See also Souza, Murilo, “Comissão proíbe implante de chips de identificação em humanos sem autorização”, *Câmara dos Deputados*, 18 August 2017.

<http://www2.camara.leg.br/camaranoticias/noticias/DIREITO-E-JUSTICA/539338-COMISSAO-PROIBE-IMPLANTE-DE-CHIPS-DE-IDENTIFICACAO-EM-HUMANOS-SEM-AUTORIZACAO.html>

⁷⁷ Brazil, “Projeto de Lei No. 6489”, 2016.

<http://www.camara.gov.br/proposicoesWeb/fichadetramitacao?idProposicao=2117288>

III - rehabilitation of the sick and disabled.⁷⁸

On the other hand, although the text does also apply to cosmetic surgeons, it is clear that a cosmetic surgery is, in most cases (except, for instance, when a cosmetic surgeon has to operate on a patient who has been badly burnt), a non-therapeutic procedure. According to the Brazilian Code of Medical Ethics (*Port.: Código de Ética Médica*), the physician must require the consent of patients, and inform them about the risks and benefits that a given procedure involves:

Chapter IV

Human rights

It is forbidden to the physician:

[...]

Article 22.

Failure to obtain consent from the patient, or their legal representative, after explaining the procedure to be performed, except in case of imminent risk of death.

[...]

Chapter XII

Teaching and medical research

It is forbidden to the physician:

[...]

Art. 101. Failure to obtain from the patient or their legal representative the free and informed consent term for conducting research involving human subjects, after due explanation about the nature and consequences of the research.⁷⁹

A patient who undergoes a cosmetic surgery has to be informed in advance about the risks involved and the prospect of achieving the desired cosmetic goals. Some cosmetic surgeons and cosmetic surgery clinics provide the consent form online, in their respective websites.⁸⁰

The Federal Medical Council (*Conselho Federal de Medicina*, or *CFM*) has issued a Resolution that states that plastic surgeons, like other surgeons, do not have civil liability for the results of the surgeries they perform.

⁷⁸ Brasil, “Lei No. 12.842”, 10 July 2013.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2013/lei/l12842.htm

⁷⁹ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Código de Ética Médica”.

<https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/stories/biblioteca/codigo%20de%20etica%20medica.pdf>. See also

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Recommendation CFM No. 1”, 2016.

https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/Recomendacoes/1_2016.pdf

⁸⁰ See for instance Hospital São Carlos, “Termo de Consentimento Informado para Cirurgia Plástica de Mamas (redução e/ou elevação)”.

http://www.hospitalsaocarlos.com.br/sites/default/files/cirurgia_plastica_de_mamas_reducao_e_ou_elevacao.pdf. See also Hospital Meridional, Termo de Consentimento Informado para Cirurgia

Plástica.http://www.hospitalmeridional.com.br/novo/arquivos/termos/10052017_161042_TERMOS_DE_CONSENTIMENTO_CIRURGIA_PLASTICA.pdf. See also Doncatto, L. F., “Uso do termo de consentimento

informado em cirurgia plástica estética”, *Jornal Brasileiro de Cirurgia Plástica*, Vol. 27 No. 3, 2012, pp. 353-358.

<http://www.scielo.br/pdf/rbcp/v27n3/03.pdf>

Art. 3 - In Plastic Surgery, as in any medical specialty, results cannot be guaranteed or guarantee the success of the treatment, and the doctor must inform the patient clearly of the benefits and risks of the procedure.

Art. 4 - The purpose of the medical act in Plastic Surgery as in all medical practice constitutes an obligation of means and not of end or result.⁸¹

Yet, this Resolution represents a violation of legislative competence, for the Constitution states that the Union has exclusive competence to legislate about private law (*Port. Direito Civil*). Therefore, a regulatory act of the Federal Medical Council cannot conflict with a federal law. The relevant federal law in this case is the Brazilian Consumer Protection Code (*Port.: Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law No. 8.078, from 11 September 1990). The Superior Court of Justice (*Port.: Superior Tribunal de Justiça*, or *STJ*) is the competent court for judging private law cases. When a patient sues a cosmetic surgeon who has failed to deliver the agreed result, STJ rules that, indeed, the cosmetic surgeon has an obligation of result, for the expectation of the result is exactly what motivates the patient to contract the services of a cosmetic surgeon, and not the cure or treatment for a disease.⁸²

4. *Is there a legal requirement for informed consent in the case of all non-therapeutic procedures? If yes, are requirements concerning informed consent more or less rigorous than in the case of procedures with a therapeutic aim?*

Yes, in some cases requirement for informed consent is clearly regulated, as for instance, tattooing and piercing services in some states and municipalities that have regulated this matter on a local level.⁸³ In other cases the legislation does not explicitly mention “informed consent”. In these cases it is, rather, required that the provider of the service provides the client with all the relevant information about the service, as for instance in the Consumer Protection Code (*Port.: Código de Defesa do Consumidor*, Law Nº 8.078, from 11 September 1990.), Article:

Article 6 The basic consumer rights are:
[...]

⁸¹ Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Resolution CFM No. 1.621”, 16 May 2001.

http://www.portalmedico.org.br/resolucoes/cfm/2001/1621_2001.htm

<https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/stories/biblioteca/codigo%20de%20etica%20medica.pdf>. See also

Conselho Federal de Medicina (CFM), “Recommendation CFM No. 1”, 2016.

https://portal.cfm.org.br/images/Recomendacoes/1_2016.pdf

⁸² See decisions by the Superior Court of Justice on this matter: STJ - REsp: 236708 MG 1999/0099099-4, Relator: Ministro CARLOS FERNANDO MATHIAS (JUIZ FEDERAL CONVOCADO DO TRF, Trial day: 10/02/2009, T4 - QUARTA TURMA, publicized: 20090518, DJe 18/05/2009 and STJ - REsp: 1180815 MG 2010/0025531-0, Relator: Ministra NANCY ANDRIGHI, trial day: 19/08/2010, T3 - TERCEIRA TURMA, publicized: DJe 26/08/2010).

⁸³ Brasil, “Lei No. 7926”, 27 March 2018.

<https://gov-rj.jusbrasil.com.br/legislacao/561225419/lei-7926-27-marco-2018-rio-de-janeiro-rj> See also

Brasil, “Lei No. 7970”, 21 May 2018.

<https://gov-rj.jusbrasil.com.br/legislacao/581017979/lei-7970-18-rio-de-janeiro-rj>

III - adequate and clear information on the different products and services, with a correct specification of quantity, characteristics, composition, quality, incidental taxes and price, as well as the risks they present;⁸⁴

A similar provision is also present in the Brazilian Civil Code (*Port.: Código Civil*, Law Nº 10.406, from 10 January 2002), Articles 15 and Article 147:

Art. 15. No one shall be compelled to submit, at risk of life, to medical treatment or surgical intervention.

[...]

Article 147.

In bilateral legal transactions, the intentional silence of one of the parties regarding fact or quality that the other party has ignored constitutes an intentional omission, proving that without it the business would not have been celebrated.⁸⁵

Although this piece of legislation does not explicitly mention “informed consent”, it does make it clear that the provider of a service may not fail to provide relevant information (“the intentional silence of one of the parties”). A relevant piece of information is one that, if had been given in advance, presumably the “business would not have been celebrated.”

5. *Has the question of the protection afforded to the augmented or modified body (e.g. body with prosthetics) been addressed nationally? Is the augmented or modified body afforded the same protection and guarantees as an organic body? Are there issues regarding ownership?*

In Brazil, the “augmented or modified body” falls under the category of “Implanted Medical Devices” (*Port.: Dispositivos Médicos Implantáveis, DMI, henceforth IMD*). The commercialization, implant, and surveillance of IMD are regulated by the Brazilian Agency for Complementary Health Care (*Port.: Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar, ANS*) and ANVISA. The documents issued by ANS and ANVISA focus on the therapeutic function of IMD, rather than their capacity to “augment” the human body. ANS defines IMD as follows:

What are Implantable Medical Devices (IMD)?

Any instrument, apparatus, equipment, software, material or article, used alone or in combination, introduced into the human body for the purpose of diagnosis, prevention, control, treatment, mitigation or compensation of an illness, injury or disability.⁸⁶

ANVISA provides a rather lengthier definition:

⁸⁴ Brasil, “Lei No. 8.078”, 11 September 1990.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078.htm.

⁸⁵ Brasil, “Código Civil Brasileiro, Lei No. 10.406”, 10 January 2002.

http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/l10406.htm

⁸⁶ Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar (ANS), “Dispositivos Médicos Implantáveis (DMI)”.

<http://www.ans.gov.br/temas-de-interesse/dispositivos-medicos-implantaveis-dmi>

Implantable medical product:

Any medical product designed to be fully introduced into the human body or to replace an epithelial or ocular surface, by means of surgical intervention, and designed to remain in place after the intervention. It is also considered to be an implantable medical product any medical product intended to be partially introduced into the human body through surgical intervention and to remain after this long-term intervention.⁸⁷

A patient who carries IMD has the same range of rights that non-users of IMD have. In addition to these rights, carriers of IMD also have the right to device traceability (*Port.:* *rastreabilidade*), i.e. the patient must be informed about the following features of the IMD they carry: name of manufacturer, ANVISA registration number, manufacturing batch number, expiration date, IMD reference number attributed by the manufacturer (figure 2).

Figure 2: ANVISA traceability label for IMD. Source: ANS, video screenshot.⁸⁸

The documents issued by ANS and ANVISA do not address specific issues regarding ownership. It must be emphasized, again, that neither ANS nor ANVISA relate IMD to HET. The capacity IMD might have to enhance or augment the human body is not examined or even mentioned in these documents.

⁸⁷Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), “Manual do Usuário da Resolução-RDC No. 185/2001 Orientações sobre Registro, Cadastramento, Alteração, Revalidação e Cancelamento do Registro de Produtos Gerência-Geral de Tecnologia de Produtos para a Saúde, ANVISA”, 2001, p. 30.

<http://www.abraidi.com.br/files/tmp-PDF/manual-da-185.pdf>. See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), *Relatório final do grupo de trabalho externo de órteses, próteses e materiais especiais (GTE OPME) ANS/ANVISA*, 2016.

http://www.ans.gov.br/images/stories/Participacao_da_sociedade/2016_gt_opme/gt-opme-relatoriointegral.pdf. See also Agência Nacional de Vigilância Sanitária (ANVISA), *Manual de Boas Práticas de Gestão das Órteses, Próteses e Materiais Especiais (OPME)*, 2016.

http://bvsm.s.saude.gov.br/bvs/publicacoes/manual_praticas_gestao_proteses_materiais_especiais.pdf

⁸⁸ Agência Nacional de Saúde Suplementar (ANS), video available at:

Dispositivos Médicos Implantáveis (DMI) <http://www.ans.gov.br/temas-de-interesse/dispositivos-medicos-implantaveis-dmi> See also “Nota Técnica Conjunta No. 001/2014 (ANVISA)”

<http://www.latinigroup.com/legislacao/NT01-2014.pdf>

4. Discussion

A growing number of articles published in Brazilian news outlets, both in the mainstream press and in science bulletins, suggests that the public at large seems to be aware that HET have the potential to affect society in a variety of ways. The use of performance enhancing drugs in professional sports and the practice of cosmetic surgeries are already well-known in Brazil. But over the last few years there have also been many reports, for instance, on the use of Ritalin and Modafinil (sold in Brazil as Stavigile) among students who seek to perform better at examinations. There have also been reports in the press on topics such as the use of IVF and PGD techniques that allow prospective parents to select a limited number of traits in the future child. The use of microchip implants for the storage of personal passwords has also been the subject of some news stories. There have also been stories about the use of high-tech prosthetic limbs that enable parathletes to run faster than most able-bodied individuals are capable of. On the other hand, these practices are not usually seen as examples of activities that fall under the broader category of HE. Although HE and HET constitute topics that have already been discussed by group philosophy scholars in Brazil, HE and HET have not been extensively discussed by legal scholars, legislators, policy makers and the public at large.

5. Conclusions

There is not in Brazil specific legislation or legal debate on HE as a category in its own right. The expression “human enhancement”, or one of its possible translations into Portuguese (*aprimoramento humano*, or *aperfeiçoamento humano*, or *melhoramento humano*) is not mentioned in legal documents. The existence of HE and HET is hardly acknowledged in the legal scholarship. Lack of legal and parliamentary debate on HE and HET contrasts with the public’s awareness that there are several devices, products, and procedures, seemingly unrelated to one another, that have the potential to augment the human body and to enhance our cognitive and physical capacities in a variety of ways. In this report, we have provided a legal analysis of several documents and pieces of legislation that regulate the research, development, commercialization, and use of such devices, products, and procedures. Most documents we have reviewed here address issues related to health, health care, medical services, and medical products. But these documents focus mainly on concepts such as treatment and rehabilitation of health, rather than HE or HET.

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